

Establishment of wheat following lowland rice in east India

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A field experiment was conducted on the economic feasibility of relay wheat cropping in the lowland rice ecosystem at Pusa (Bihar) during 1993-94 and 1994-95. It used a split-plot design with three replications and six methods of wheat crop establishment in the main plot and three seed rates in the subplot. The soil was silty clay, pH 8.4 (1:2.5, soil:water), with initial nutrient status of 262 kg N ha⁻¹, 34.5 kg P ha⁻¹, and 110 kg K ha⁻¹. A long-duration traditional aman rice variety, Sudha, was transplanted under normal practices in both the years and the wheat variety Sonali was grown according to treatments listed in the table. In relay cropping, wheat seeds were broadcast 10-12 d before harvest in standing rice to avoid delayed seeding. Three seed rates, i.e., 125, 150, and 175 kg ha⁻¹ were with all subplot treatments. Wheat crops were also raised by normal practices, except for relay and zero tillage. In relay cropping, fertilizer was used after the first irrigation.

In wheat cultivated in the lowlands, *Chenopodium album*, followed by *Launia pinnatifide*, is the dominant weed where

wheat is tilled. In relay cultivation, *L. pinnatifide* is the dominant weed in early growth and later *Cyperus rotundus* and *Cynodon dactylon* become dominant. More or less the same trend is observed in all plots where preparatory tillage is not done.

The maximum grain equivalent yield (see table) was recorded under T6, which was superior to all treatments except T5. Relay practice and paraquat

application with different sets of minimum tillage (T1, T2, and T3) were statistically alike and ranked second. Therefore, sowing wheat in well-prepared field is advisable. If land is not ready for plowing, relay or minimum tillage are also advisable. The same trend was observed for economic return. A 150 kg ha⁻¹ seed rate was profitable irrespective of crop establishment methods. ■

Effect of wheat crop establishment method and seed rate treatment on yield and economic return in a lowland rice ecosystem. Bihar, India, 1993-95.

Treatment	Yield in terms of wheat equivalent (t ha ⁻¹)		Economic return (US\$ ha ⁻¹)		Benefit-cost ratio	
	Grain	Straw	Gross	Net		
Method of wheat crop establishment						
T1	Relay cropping (sowing in standing rice crop on 25 Nov)	4.3	5.4	572	307	2.15
T2	Paraquat application @ 2.0 kg ha ⁻¹ just after rice harvest and sowing at 24 h after that by hand plowing on 6 Dec	4.5	5.5	592	321	2.18
T3	Paraquat application, rototilling (once) and sowing behind the hand plow on 10 Dec	4.3	5.7	574	302	2.11
T4	Rototilling twice and sowing behind the hand plow on 10 Dec	4.2	5.5	554	277	2.00
T5	M.B. plow (once) + rototilling (once) and sowing behind the hand plow on 12 Dec	4.6	6.2	617	335	2.18
T6	M.B. plow (once) + rototilling twice and sowing behind the hand plow on 12 Dec	4.8	6.4	635	346	2.20
LSD (0.05)						
	0.2	0.3	26	14	0.15	
Seed rate (kg ha ⁻¹)						
	S1 - 125	4.2	5.6	561	292	2.09
	S2 - 150	4.5	6.1	600	328	2.20
	S3 - 175	4.7	6.3	628	351	2.10
	LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.3	29	18	0.10

Postharvest technology

Stripper harvesting improvements meet Chinese needs

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Stripping grain, as a method of harvesting rice, was introduced into this Hangzhou institute in 1994 when we first tested the IRRI-designed SG800 system. This system represents the

Stripper-reaper system for rice harvesting.